

Methodological Notes File

Heuristic Map, Analytical Procedure, and Manual Interpretive Process

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1. Purpose of This Document

This file provides a brief account of the interpretive framework used to analyse eight Pakistani television commercials from the 1980s–2020s. It clarifies the analytical steps, documents the heuristic map (H1–H6), and confirms that all observations and interpretations were performed manually. This enhances transparency and allows readers to see how theoretical constructs were linked to multimodal evidence.

2. Interpretive Nature of CDA/MCDS

This study follows the tradition of **Critical Discourse Analysis** and **Multimodal Critical Discourse Studies**, which approach discourse as a socially and ideologically charged practice rather than a numerical dataset. In this paradigm:

- Meaning is **interpreted**, not counted.
- Patterns are identified through **close, iterative reading and viewing**, not through software-based coding.
- The analysis aims to understand how **language, image, sound, and space** work together to naturalise social norms.
- Multimodal evidence is examined **holistically**, with attention to how cues cluster and align.

The purpose is not to produce statistics but to understand **how** certain forms of modernity, gender, class, and affect are represented and normalised.

3. Heuristic Map (H1–H6)

The following heuristic map guided the analytic process. It is **not** a coding scheme or algorithm; it is a conceptual map linking **abstract constructs** to **observable multimodal cues** that repeatedly occurred across the corpus.

Some early, weaker or inconsistent cues that I later dropped are kept in **strike-through** to show the exploratory nature of the analysis.

H1. Wellness / Ease

Typical cues:

- Calm conversational tones
- ~~Any explicit mention of “doctors” or “experts”~~ (not consistently tied to wellness across all ads)
- ~~Quick references to “morning” or “night” routines~~ (too diffuse as an indicator)
- Soft ambient sound rather than loud jingles
- Lexis of comfort, balance, “strength,” and ease
- Composed facial expressions without visible panic

Analytic use: Indicates how modern care practices are framed as self-regulation rather than burden or duty.

H2. Parity / Partnership

Typical cues:

- Eye-level two-shots that place both partners at the same height
- ~~Occasional mirroring in posture or hand placement~~ (not stable enough to rely on)
- Balanced framing of male–female pairs within the same visual weight – in 1908s, mixed gendered class but gender segregated seating
- Coordinated gestures (e.g. shared nods, joint turning towards the product)
- ~~Shared use of “we” and “our” in a short span~~ (not counted systematically)

Analytic use: Tracks the shift from paternal guardianship to aestheticised partnership in commercial representation.

H3. Mobility / Aspiration

Typical cues:

- Airport lounges, transit spaces, or travel-related interiors
- ~~Visible luggage or boarding passes~~ (marked early on, later judged too literal and inconsistent)
- Smooth lateral camera movement suggesting ease of movement
- Business-like attire in otherwise casual scenes (colonial culture?)
- Forward-leaning posture or slight movement towards exits or doors
- ~~Presence of English signage in the background~~ (noted a few times but dropped as an unreliable mobility marker)

Analytic use: Helps trace how aspiration is visualised without overstating upward class mobility.

H4. Pedagogic Order

Typical cues:

- Classroom mise-en-scène (desks, board, teacher–student layout)
- Teacher’s spatial position (central vs side, elevated vs level)
- ~~Raising hands vs silent listening~~ (watched for this but not used consistently in the final analysis)
- Chalkboard versus glossy visual aids, screens, or props (**practical to mention minutiae ???**)
- Globe, world map, or aspirational decor signalling outward-looking education

Analytic use: Highlights how learning is framed as reciprocal (1980s) or performative (2018), revealing shifting understandings of authority.

H5. Affective Temperature

Typical cues:

- Crowd noise and chanting versus soft acoustic beds or gentle background music

- ~~Number of cuts per 10 seconds~~ (briefly trialled as a rough proxy for intensity, then abandoned)
- Elevated volume and mass cheering versus subdued, one-to-one talk
- Rhythm and tempo of editing (fast sequences vs lingering, steady shots)
- ~~Overt exclamations in dialogue (e.g. “wah!”, “wow!”)~~ (found too scattered to be a reliable stand-alone cue)

Analytic use: Used to identify how emotional life is reorganised from mass euphoria to controlled composure.

H6. Domestic Moral Frame

Typical cues:

- Dining tables, sofas, and living-room interiors as key decision spaces
- Family photographs, framed images, or home ornaments in the background
- Soft frontal lighting with warm tones around family interactions
- ~~Specific decor trends or furniture styles~~ (noticed casually, then dropped as irrelevant to the main argument)
- Slower pacing and quieter sound design in domestic sequences (???)

Analytic use: Anchors new practices of wellness, planning, and aspiration in familiar domestic rituals, revealing how “change” is domesticated.

4. How the Heuristics Were Used (Manual Interpretive Process)

The heuristics were applied through the following **manual** steps:

1. **Repeated viewing** of each commercial (over several years in some cases).
2. **Noting timestamps** where specific multimodal cues appeared (gaze shifts, sound changes, camera movement, lexical choices).
3. **Comparing ads in pairs** (1980s vs 2010s/2020s) to trace diachronic re-patterning.
4. **Recording observations** in handwritten and typed notes (see separate “Corpus Log”).

5. **Mapping cues to constructs** when several indicators aligned (e.g., warm palette + two-shot + shared smile → parity-as-composure), while discarding weaker or inconsistent cues (shown in strike-through above).
6. **Cross-checking patterns** across all eight ads to identify convergence (e.g., wellness lexicon plus polite affect across product categories).
7. **Synthesising findings** through CDA principles of recontextualisation, legitimisation, and evaluative stance.

No automated coding tools, statistical programs, or AI classification systems were used at any stage of corpus analysis.

5. Manual Authorship Statement

I confirm that:

- All multimodal observations, interpretive steps, and thematic synthesis were performed **manually**.
- No AI system contributed to identifying patterns, interpreting data, or generating analytical claims.
- The heuristics were conceptual guides, not computational models.
- All interpretations reflect my own academic judgement and long-term engagement with the corpus.